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Intersectionality in EU Law and Policy Deliberative Democracy at a Crossroads

Executive summary

Intersectionality is an area still to be explored within the European Union and particularly in the context of deliberative democracy mechanisms, such as citizens' assemblies.

As part of the EU-CIEMBLY project, which aims at providing the analytical framework and the prototype of an EU Citizens' Assembly that encompasses intersectionality, a review of legal and policy documents addressing intersectionality in the EU has been developed, so as to identify the shortcomings or gaps that should be addressed by the relevant bodies.

The main findings of the first year of the project are presented in this policy brief, which also contains recommendations on the operationalisation of intersectionality in the policy areas of the European Union, especially in deliberative democracy.

Particularly, intersectionality should be better defined, according to a clear analytical framework, and integrated extensively into all relevant policy but also legal documents of the EU, which would allow exploring the full range of a developing intersectionality toolbox that includes strategic but also binding measures.

On this behalf, more guidance from the EU is required in its various fields of action. The "Union of Equality" is still in need of improvements, but it is in the deliberative arena that the EU – as a main actor in promoting and delivering mini-public formats – has the most to offer in terms of developing an intersectional embedded approach for Citizens' Assemblies.

Background

Since the Lisbon Treaty, the democratic legitimacy of the EU is based not only in representative democracy but also in participatory democracy. Thus, Article 10(3) of the Treaty on European Union (TEU) enshrines that 'every citizen shall have the right to participate in the democratic life of the Union. Decisions shall be taken as openly and as closely as possible to the citizen'.

It is within this context that besides consultative-type mechanisms and the hybrid European Citizens' Initiative, different mechanisms of **deliberative democracy** began to emerge.

One of the large-scale examples was precisely the Conference on the Future of Europe held from April 2021 to May 2022. Since then, five

European Citizens' Panels have been conducted, further integrating deliberative democracy into the work of the European Union.

In addition to these Union-level developments, a multitude of mini-publics, mainly **citizens' assemblies**, are being held throughout the different Member States.

Nevertheless, those deliberative mechanisms have not always considered issues of intersectionality, nor have they set out to adopt an intersectional approach.

Indeed, **intersectionality** in general is an area yet to be explored in greater depth within the EU, although there is growing recognition of the importance of intersectional equality by the European institutions, mostly under a soft law approach.

The EU-CIEMBLY project combines both developing realities – deliberative democracy and intersectionality – and is therefore in a good position to provide recommendations on how to operationalise intersectionality into the policy areas of the European Union, especially in deliberative democracy.

Statement of the issue

The European Union did not define 'intersectionality' in a legal act until the adoption of Directive (EU) 2023/970. This Directive and others that have followed it perpetuate the shortcomings of the scattered non-discrimination legislation of the EU. Indeed, EU anti-discrimination legislation addresses only the few **protected grounds** covered in an exhaustive way by Article 10 of the TEU and article 19 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). Apart from this, references to intersectionality in EU law are sparse.

Similar shortcomings arise in the documents of the European institutions that have no binding force. For instance, the five Strategies of the Union of Equality framework insist on compartmentalisation, thus showing a **limited view of intersectional discrimination**.

However, both in these Strategies and in other policy documents, mainly from the European Parliament, an intersectional approach is beginning to be explicitly incorporated. Despite this, these policy documents fail to incorporate operational measures. Thus, the focus on aspirational measures leads to a more theoretical commitment to mainstreaming intersectionality.

Box 1. What is intersectionality?

- Concept coined by Kimberlé Crenshaw in 'Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Antiracist Politics' (1989).
- Originally described how race and gender intersect in the experiences of Black women, it soon began to be applied to other characteristics.
- Intersectionality is a context-dependent concept but has found already some working definitions within the EU such as

the one proposed by EIGE: A “analytical tool for studying, understanding and responding to the ways in which sex and gender intersect with other personal characteristics/identities, and how these intersections contribute to unique experiences of discrimination”.

- For the EU-Ciembly project (Deliverable 2.2., p. 35) "Intersectionality emphasises that social categorisations such as race, class, gender, sexual orientation, and physical ability are not independent and isolated, but rather intersect to create overlapping interdependent systems of discrimination and marginalisation”

In other matters, the weaknesses of the consultative-nature mechanisms to enhance the participation of citizens in the European Union led to the emergence of new proposals that focus on deliberation. One of these mechanisms are **citizens' assemblies**. However, despite their success in participatory terms, they are not designed to address intersectional consideration. On the contrary, they stick to traditional means to make participation more inclusive, such as ensuring gender or youth balance, reflecting in the recruitment the demographic diversity or trying to fight the discrimination resulting from the digital divide.

It is therefore necessary for policymakers to pay attention to these issues, starting with intersectionality across the various fields of action of the European Union and then moving on to the specific one of deliberative democracy.

Summary of findings

Intersectionality in general

The European directives' conceptualisation of intersectionality only focuses on the few protected grounds of EU anti-discrimination legislation. By contrast, Article 21 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU and Article 14 of the European Convention on Human Rights includes a broader list of grounds and in a non-exhaustive way.

Going even beyond the field of discrimination, other directives and policy documents refer to different **social groups**. They also adopt a broader perspective on the concept of intersectionality, as they address not only identity factors but also underlying **power**

structures. For example, Directive (EU) 2024/1385 recognises that ‘victims experiencing intersectional discrimination are at a heightened risk of violence’.

Figure 1. Protected grounds and social groups

Although most of the measures to address intersectionality contained in European legislation and policy documents lack tangible impact, there are some exceptions. For instance, in Article 16(3) and Article 23(3) of Directive (EU) 2023/970 which recognise intersectional discrimination as an aggravating factor for compensation and penalties. Another one can be found in Article 21(g) of Directive (EU) 2024/1712, which refers to the need to include in the guidelines for law enforcement and prosecutorial authorities’ guidance on how to cater for enhanced protection and all relevant support needs of victims experiencing intersectional discrimination.

Regarding policy documents, the LGBTIQ Equality Strategy 2020-2025 and the Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 explicitly mention the use of intersectionality as a cross-cutting principle to implement them. On an institutional level, the Gender Equality Strategy creates a Task Force for Equality that should pursue an intersectional approach in mainstreaming equality.

Besides, the European Parliament Resolution of 6 July 2022 on ‘intersectional discrimination in the European Union: the socio-economic situation of women of African, Middle-Eastern, Latin-American and Asian descent’ defines several specific operational measures to mitigate intersectional discrimination.

All of them can serve as an inspiration for a more extensive **toolbox** to effectively mainstream, share and disseminate intersectionality across the European Union and Member States (Deliverable 2.4, annex III).

Figure 2. Measures to operationalise intersectionality

The legal delimitation of intersectionality and the lack of its recognition as a specific category of discrimination is reflected in the process of recognising intersectionality in case law. The Court of Justice of the European Union has not yet embedded an intersectional approach into its reasoning. This was clear, for instance, in the *Parris Case (C-443/15 – David L Parris v. Trinity College Dublin and Others)*, in which the Court found that there is ‘no new category of discrimination resulting from the combination of more than one of those grounds, such as sexual orientation and age, that may be found to exist where discrimination on the basis of those grounds taken in isolation has not been established’.

Although the Court insists on maintaining a formal position regarding the individual grounds of discrimination, it has already recognised the inclusion into a single category of multidimensional and intersectional traits that intimately link women subject to violence and seeking migrant status (*C-621/21 – WS v. Intervyuirasht organ na Darzhavna agentsia za bezhantsite pri Ministerskia savet*).

Intersectionality in deliberative democracy

The policy review analysed EU policy documents that address deliberative democracy, as to identify signs that would indicate that the EU advocates for citizen participation according to parameters of intersectional equality, inclusion and deliberation.

Table 1. Intersectional equality, inclusion and deliberation according to EU-CIEMBLY Deliverable 2.2

<p>Intersectional equality</p>	<p>Treating some groups differently to achieve genuine equality in participation or inclusion. Recognition of a more expansive conception of discrimination</p>
<p>Intersectional inclusion</p>	<p>Prioritising the inclusion of marginalised groups over representativeness. Consider power imbalances and biases to include those with intersectional views. Consider intersectionality in the organisation, experts, facilitators and other staff</p>
<p>Intersectional deliberation</p>	<p>Recognising barriers for some social groups in expressing their viewpoints. Consider that biases and power dynamics influence communication among participants</p>

Two main conclusions were drawn from the analysis. First, these documents do not always focus on deliberative democracy, nor on citizens' assemblies, but on general citizens' participation. Second, even though it appears to be a slight evolution in terms of inclusion and intersectionality, the parameters of intersectional equality, inclusion and deliberation are not fully covered, for instance:

O There are no specific mentions on the participation of People belonging to Multiple Intersecting Marginalised Groups (PMIMG).

Box 2. What does the EU-CIEMBLY Project mean by PMIMG?

Individuals who belong to two or more marginalised groups and subsequently experience unique, intersecting and complex forms of marginalisation in society. They often face extreme forms of marginalisation due to the belongingness to several marginalised groups simultaneously.

O Discrimination in participatory mechanisms is not analysed in depth by the EU institutions. Only a few references can be found in relation to very specific aspects such as discrimination resulting from the digital divide.

O The processes of sampling and recruitment are not adjusted to intersectionality. Only demographic criteria and gender and age quotas are considered. Furthermore, the specific role of civil society organisations in drawing out and conducting Citizens' Assemblies is lacking.

O One of the major gaps in the documents analysed is the lack of definition of intersectional avenues in the deliberative phase. For instance, how to empower PMIMG to make themselves heard and their voices count.

Recommendations

As a consequence of the work developed during the first year of the EU-CIEMBLY project, the following recommendations may be drawn:

1 Define intersectionality

The definition of intersectionality should cover the intersection of different protected grounds as well as underline discrimination due to power structures, which could allow for a consideration of protected grounds other than those currently included in anti-discrimination law. This definition should be integrated in the EU's Plans and Strategies in all relevant policy areas (and not only in the Equality field) but also be included in binding EU instruments that should provide reinforced guarantees or specific measures for people that, given their particular intersections, are at odds with reinforced forms of marginalisation.

2 Integrate intersectionality as a transversal concern in legal and policy instruments

Intersectionality should be inserted clearly and explicitly into policy and legal instruments as a transversal concern, although adjusted to each specific field, molding the way those instruments should be redefined, interpreted and applied. Therefore, alongside other transversal EU concerns, the Commission's "Better regulation" toolbox should be adjusted in order to include methodologies to embed intersectionality into its impact assessments, evaluations, and fitness checks.

3 Develop an intersectionality toolbox

A robust intersectionality toolbox should be developed as a method to mainstream intersectionality demands and concerns. This means going beyond integrating intersectionality into impact assessments and in monitoring and evaluation and move towards more concrete and operational measures adjusted to each area of regulation, ranging from educational, mediation and organisational measures to more stringent infringement and sanctioning provisions, that may be imposed upon on the national levels.

4 Emphasise the interconnectedness of different types of discrimination

From an intersectional perspective, some of the European Union's major strategies, such as the 'Union of Equality', ought to be revised as different types of discrimination should not be treated as isolated compartments but highlighting their interconnectedness. Besides each including a clear intersectional approach based on a similar analytical framework, those EU strategies should reflect concrete intersecting inequalities in their areas of regulation (for instance in housing or energy), going beyond, in some cases, a purely gender-based approach.

5 Reinforce collaboration between equality bodies

Ideally, the organisation of equality bodies dedicated to specific protected grounds should not be allowed to prevent a global consideration of the many faces of discriminatory phenomena, or effective collaboration between equality bodies should be reinforced, for intersectional discrimination to be effectively tackled. This should be taken in particular consideration when implementing Directives 2024/1499 and 2024/1500 on standards for equality bodies.

6 Broaden the concept of inclusion considered in CAs

The concept of inclusion currently considered in CAs should be broadened, as it is not enough to fully address essential issues such as sampling and recruitment, once it only considers demographic or attitudinal criteria and overlooks other possible methods that may be used, such as the involvement of civil society organisations. The EU should provide more guidance on cases in which traditional sampling and recruiting mechanisms may not be the most fitted mechanisms to integrate inclusive and intersectional

concerns, moreover when the EU itself has been adopting to certain specific deliberative formats, such as youth assemblies.

7 Target underrepresented groups in the recruitment process of CAs

The recruitment process should specifically target underrepresented groups as intersectional equality may need to break barriers to the participation of many other different groups, depending on the relevant intersections, not only young people. Thus, policy documents from the EU should address the participation of PMIMG or intersecting groups, including but not limited to age and gender. The development of stakeholder mapping methodologies (given the difficulties in collecting and accessing data on certain characteristics) and guiding documents of ensuring participation of underrepresented groups by the EU would be most welcomed.

8 Consider intersectional inclusion within the staff members

The bodies and the staff participating in the CAs, including experts, chairs and particularly facilitators should be selected taking also into account intersectional inclusion; gender-balance is not enough and other grounds of discrimination or membership of a social group should be considered, so that there is a greater diversity in staff members. Additionally, training for experts, facilitators and chairs before the start of the process should include specific guidelines to ensure inclusion. The EU should provide checklists or develop courses that have intersectionality at heart to promote good practices at the EU and Member States level.

9 Develop creative forms of deliberation and innovative techniques

Policy documents should consider each specific phase of a deliberative mechanism, particularly the deliberative phase, which is often the most overlooked. Creative forms of deliberation are needed, and more reflection should be given to the deliberative aspect of CAs when addressing these issues in policy documents. Developing innovative techniques that facilitate engagement in the debate, regardless of the difficulties in expressing someone's views, and reimagining how the outcomes of the CAs may be produced should be an issue of concern for upcoming CAs organized by the EU.

10 Increase dialogue with other organisations in deliberative democracy

In general, a deeper dialogue and desirably joint initiatives with other organisations, such as the OECD and the Council of Europe, that also have an agenda on deliberative democracy and inclusion could be a step forward in achieving a better and shared understanding of intersectionality in general and in CAs all throughout Europe.

FURTHER READING

Muñoz Benito, L. & Lopes, D. (2024). *Policy Scoping Review of the European Union Policy on Intersectionality, including Intersectionality within the Context of Citizen's Assemblies*, EU-CIEMBLY Deliverable 2.4. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17608196>

Karatzia, A., & O'Connor, N. (2025). *Analytical and Normative Framework*, EU-CIEMBLY Deliverable 2.2., version 2. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17607956>

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EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

Email: eu-ciembly@ij.uc.pt

www.eu-ciembly.eu
